

complex on Laboratory experimental fields at Hawalbagh (1,250 msl) and cultivator fields at varied elevations and with different agroclimatic conditions. About 40 insects have been identified in rice crops (see table).

The most serious damage is caused by the pink borer *Sesamia inferens* Wlk. Although the pest is active from the beginning of July to the end of September, the infestation peaks at 50-60% in mid-September.

Leafhopper *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* Guenée maximum intensity occurs from mid-August to early September. A number of species of grasshoppers, such as *Oxya fuscovittata* (Marschall) and *Trigonidium cicindeloides* Rambur, cause damage at all growth stages, including the nursery stage. Other important insect pests identified are the whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera* (Horv.), pentatomid bugs *Dolycoris indicus* Stål and *Nezara* sp. and

Major insect pests of rice in the hills of Uttar Pradesh, India.

Insect pest	Growth stage	Damage
<i>Heteronychus lioderes</i>	Seedling stage	Root damage (grubs and adults)
<i>Anomala dimidiata</i> var. <i>barbata</i> ; <i>Popillia cupricollis</i> ; <i>Holotrichia seticollis</i> ; other species	Seedling to dough	Root damage (grubs); leaf feeding and head damage (adults)
<i>Oxya fuscovittata</i> , <i>Trigonidium cicindeloides</i> , and other species	Seedling emergence to maturity	Leaf feeding (nymphs and adults)
<i>Sesamia inferens</i>	Tillering to dough	Stem tunneling (larvae)
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	Booting to dough	Feeding on leaf tissue, except epidermis (larvae)
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	Flowering to dough	Leaf and stem sucking (nymphs and adults)
<i>Dolycoris indicus</i> and <i>Nezara</i> sp.	Heading to dough	Leaf and grain sucking (nymphs and adults)
<i>Leptocorisa acuta</i>	Milky stage	Grain sucking (nymphs and adults)

gundhi bug *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thumb).

A number of species of white grub—including *Anomala dimidiata* var. *barbata* Burm., *Popillia cupricollis* Hope, and *Holotrichia seticollis* Moser—were found in dryland rice. *Heteronychus lioderes* was found to cause considerable damage to the nursery stage of irrigated rice in medium altitude areas. Grubs as well as adults were found feeding on rice roots. ■

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Chemical control of gall midge

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Applying granular insecticides such as carbofuran, mephosfolan, chlorfenvinphos, quinalphos, and phorate and dipping seedling roots in chlorpyrifos and chlorfenvinphos before planting have been the only effective chemical control methods against gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood Mason), both in the nursery and the main field. This study attempted to develop additional methods of insecticide application.

Twelve wettable powders were evaluated for treating sprouted seeds before sowing. Seedlings 15 and 30 days old were exposed to gall midge adults. Effectiveness was judged on appearance of silver shoots. At 16 g ai./kg seed, Evisect (San 155 90 SP), carbaryl (Sevin 50 WP), cartap hydrochloride (Padan 50 SP), Macbal (50 WP), chlordimeform (Galecron 50 WP), and MIPC (50 WP) caused either poor crop stand or phytotoxicity. Isofenphos completely sup-

pressed gall formation up to 30 days in the nursery and persisted 15 days after transplanting in the greenhouse. Carbofuran showed moderate effectiveness up to 15 days after sowing. Knockbal, fenitrothion, Imidan, and bendiocarb were ineffective.

In another test, seven insecticides were evaluated for soaking sprouted seeds before sowing. Isofenphos wettable powder and emulsifiable concentrate were effective at 0.5% in 3-hour treatments. Chlorpyrifos was effective at 0.5% in 3-hour treatments. Carbofuran, monocrotophos, BMPC, and FMC 35001 were not effective.

In a seedling root dip treatment, 0.02% chlorpyrifos was effective in 12-hour treatments or with 1% urea in 3-hour treatments. In the greenhouse, isofenphos and chlorpyrifos suppressed gall midge development up to 25 days after planting. Further experiments using the two insecticides and superphosphate slurry showed that a 1- to 2-minute dipping period was sufficient for control up to 25 days.

Thirteen granular insecticides were evaluated against different age maggots. Mephosfolan, carbofuran, and isofen-

phos at 2 kg ai./ha effectively checked silver shoot formation even when applied 7 days after gall midge maggots entered the plant tissues. Mephosfolan at 0.5 and 1.0 kg a.i./ha and carbofuran at 1 kg a.i./ha controlled maggots that had entered 3 days earlier. Chlorfenvinphos, MIPC, phorate, fensulfthion, and AC64475 at 2 kg a.i./ha checked silver shoot formation when applied 3 days after maggot entry. Quinalphos and terbufos killed maggots within one day of entry. Insecticides applied 8 days after maggot entry killed some maggots, but silver shoots formed. ■

Activity of insecticides applied in the root zone to control brown planthopper and green leafhopper

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Carbofuran provides longer residual activity and greater safety to certain predators when applied into the rice root zone than when applied as foliar spray or paddy water broadcast. IRRI entomologists and engineers are collabo-